

Updated catalog of world fossil Cantharidae, with description of two new species, plus taxonomic information

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<https://zoobank.org/17215209-386D-4ABD-8556-E5BA0B8F3C52>

Abstract: An updated catalogue of the world's fossil Cantharidae is provided and some taxonomic acts are proposed: *Poinarelektronmiles* Fanti & Damgaard, 2020 **bonum genus**; *Poinarelektronmiles ellenbergeri* Fanti & Damgaard, 2020 **comb. rest.**; *Poinarelektronmiles cuaroni* Bramanti & Fanti, 2022 **comb. rest.**; *Sanaungulus lethi* Fanti & Damgaard, 2020 **comb. rest.**; *Sanaungulus dominikiweissbachi* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022 **comb. rest.**; *Sanaungulus kachinensis* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022 **comb. rest.**; *Trapezioceps longelytrus* Kundera, Packova, Li, Hsiao, Shaw, Ferreira, Bai & Cai, 2023 **unjustified emendation**; *Sanaungulus angustipennis* (Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024b) **comb. nov.**; *Burmomiles angustipennis* Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024a **unavailable name**; *Sanaungulus dentatus* (Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024b) **comb. nov.**; *Burmomiles dentatus* Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024a **unavailable name**; *Sanaungulus recticollis* (Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024b) **comb. nov.**; *Sanaungulus ruficollis* Y. Yang, H. Liu & W. Zhao, 2022 **inappropriate name**; *Sanaungulus strunzei* Fanti & Damgaard, 2019 **comb. rest.** returns to the genus *Sanaungulus* as in the original description; *Sanaungulus undecimus* Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024a **incertae sedis** because it is clearly not a *Sanaungulus*. Additional taxonomic information is also presented, and two new species: *Mimoplatycis usa* **sp. nov.** from Eocene Rovno amber, and *Electronycha arturmichalskii* **sp. nov.** from Baltic amber are illustrated and described.

Keywords: checklist, new taxon, paleoentomology, soldier beetles, systematic, worldwide

Introduction

The study of fossil soldier beetles (family Cantharidae Imhoff, 1856) has always been rather limited, with the first comprehensive world catalog (Fanti, 2017) counting 53 species. In the past several years, the number of studies, and therefore the number of species, have increased considerably (233 species have already been described). In the meantime, reports, checklists, or updates thereof, of fossil soldier beetles have appeared, but only limited to fauna embedded in Burmese amber or Cretaceous deposits (Ross, 2017abc, 2018abc, 2019ab, 2020, 2021ab, 2022ab, 2023, 2024a, 2024b; Bramanti & Fanti, 2022; Zhao et al., 2022; Qu et al., 2023; Beutel et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2024a), plus an almost complete list of all the extinct and extant genera of

Cantharidae (Motyka et al., 2023). There is still a lot of work to be done and new species and discoveries will certainly be added in the coming years. Two new fossil taxa are presented here: a new fossil *Electronycha* Kazantsev, 2013 (extinct tribe Cacomorphocerini Fanti & Kupryjanowicz, 2018) from Baltic amber, and a new fossil *Mimoplatycis* Kazantsev, 2013 (extinct tribe Mimoplatycini Kazantsev, 2013) from Eocene Rovno amber.

Materials and methods

Description of new species

The amber piece from Rovno (western Ukraine) was cleaned and re-polished, and the inclusion was pho-

tographed by Aleksej Damzen (Vilnius, Lithuania) with a Canon 90D camera with a macro lens Canon MPE-65 mm. Extended depth of field at high magnifications was achieved by stacking multiple images from a range of focal planes using Helicon Focus v. 6.0.18 software, and the final images were edited to create figures using Adobe Photoshop 7.0. The amber piece from the Baltic Sea coasts (probably Russia), was cleaned and re-polished, and the inclusion was photographed by Artur Michalski (Wrocław, Poland) with a digital camera Canon EOS 4000D on stereobinocular microscope SMZ800 + SMZ1500 with PLAN APO lens and achieved by stacking multiple images. The plates were processed with a PhotoImpact Viewer SE program by the author of this paper. The amber pieces discussed here are preserved in the amber collection of the author Fabrizio Fanti (Piazzese, Siena, Tuscany, Italy).

Catalogue of fossil Cantharidae

In the present paper, attention was paid to all the literature on fossil Cantharidae, and to all reported species with the exception of the Pleistocene-Holocene species, as they are still living taxa, and they are already listed in Fanti (2017). However, at least one recent work must be added to this list (Gurina et al., 2024). For each species the following information are mentioned: 1) name; 2) author(s) with date. Furthermore, the taxa are listed in alphabetic-taxonomical order (only in alphabetical order for the checklist of the extinct fossil genera), and the age is given for fossiliferous horizons. This catalog is updated through 31 December 2024. The taxonomy is based on the rules of the ICZN (1999).

Results

Two new species: *Electronycha arturmichalskii* and *Mimoplatycis usa* are described below: taxonomic data, differential diagnosis and morphological description are reported.

Order Coleoptera Linnaeus, 1758
Suborder Polyphaga Emery, 1886
Infraorder Elateriformia Crowson, 1960
Superfamily Elateroidea Leach, 1815

Family Cantharidae Imhoff, 1856
Subfamily Cantharinae Imhoff, 1856
Tribe Cacomorphocerini Fanti & Kupryjanowicz, 2018
Genus *Electronycha* Kazantsev, 2013

Electronycha arturmichalskii sp. nov. (Fig. 1)

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[3177E90D-B067-4AFD-BE74-DEB95996403A](https://zoobank.org/3177E90D-B067-4AFD-BE74-DEB95996403A)

Type locality. Baltic Sea coasts, specific locality unknown (probably Russia, Kaliningrad region).

Type horizon. Middle Eocene: Lutetian (47.8–41.2 mya) to late Eocene: Priabonian (37.8–33.9 mya).

Holotype. Male, in Baltic amber, deposited in the Fabrizio Fanti amber collection, accession No. BaA10RU? (donum Artur Michalski).

Differential diagnosis. Currently, only one male and one female of *Electronycha prussica* Kazantsev, 2013 are known (Kazantsev, 2013, 2020). However, given that the genus *Electronycha* Kazantsev, 2013 comprises more species, the isolated female hypothesised to be of *E. prussica* (Kazantsev, 2020), could actually belong to any other species of the genus. The new species *E. arturmichalskii* differs from the male of *E. prussica* by its pronotum, which is less pronounced at the anterior margin and by its very different antennomeres, in particular with the antennomeres VI-IX robust, enlarged but not distally swollen (Kazantsev, 2013).

Description. Adult, winged, slender. Male defined on the basis of the eight visible sternites, with the last one triangular-shaped. Body length: about 7.0 mm. Entirely dark brown.

Head almost completely exposed, very slightly convex, moderately wide, equipped with shallow punctation. Eyes large, spherical, prominent, inserted in the upper-lateral part of the head. Mandibles elongated. Maxillary palpi 4-segmented, with last palpomere elongated, elliptical. Labial palp 3-segmented. Antennae 15-segmented, moderately long, slightly surpassing the half of elytra; antennomere I elongated, very robust; antennomere II short, slightly bulged from centre to apex, approximately 2.8 times shorter than first; antennomeres III-IX robust, enlarged and not distally swollen, antennomere III the most robust one, antennomeres IV-VI less robust than

Fig. 1. *Electronychna arturmichalskii* sp. nov. in Baltic amber, holotype. (A) Lateral view, scale bar = 1.0 mm; (B) amber piece in global view, scale bar = 0.3 mm; (C) detail of antenna, scale bar = 0.5 mm; (D) detail of last ventrites, scale bar = 0.1 mm.

the previous one (antennomere VI very slightly shorter than antennomere V), antennomeres VII-IX slightly less robust and slightly shorter than antennomeres IV-VI; antennomeres X-XIV almost filiform and progressively slightly shorter from one to the next; antennomere XV slender, filiform, rounded at apex; all antennomeres pubescent. Pronotum slightly transverse, surface bulged posteriorly and equipped with scattered and long setae, anterior margin very slightly produced (extruded), sides straight, posterior margin straight and slightly bordered, corners rounded, obtuse. Scutellum triangular-shaped. Elytra elongated, covering the last abdominal segment, parallel-sided, wider than pronotum, rounded at apex, surface wrinkled equipped with sparse and long setae. Metathoracic wings infusate, covered by elytra. Legs long, rather robust, pubescent; coxae short, massive; trochanters elongated, enlarged from centre to apex, rounded apically; femora cylindrical, robust; tibiae cylindrical, thin. Tarsi 5-segmented; first tarsomere elongated, very robust; second and third tarsomere

short and very wide laterally and almost flat; tarsomere IV strongly bilobed, rounded; tarsomere V thin, very elongated, curved, enlarged from centre to apex; claws simple. Metasternum robust, with the posterior margin rounded and slightly incised in the middle. Abdomen with eight transverse visible sternites, pubescent; last tergite elongated with sides enveloping and folded; last sternite triangular-shaped, smaller than last tergite.

Etymology. Named after an author's dear friend: Artur Robert Michalski (Wrocław, Poland), great and consummate expert on amber inclusions.

Syninclusions. Detritus, botanical remains (including stellate hairs), air bubbles, and probably a Diptera ("hidden").

Remarks. The yellow amber piece, stalactite-shaped, measures approximately 23×10×6 mm. The inclusion is clearly visible only on one side, and appears complete except for one leg (perhaps detached and partially present). The female is unknown.

Fig. 2. *Mimoplatycis usa* sp. nov. in Rovno amber, holotype. (A) Dorsal view, scale bar = 0.5 mm; (B) ventral view (largely covered by white emulsion), scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Subfamily Malthininae Kiesenwetter, 1852
Tribe Mimoplatycini Kazantsev, 2013
Genus *Mimoplatycis* Kazantsev, 2013

Mimoplatycis usa sp. nov. (Figs 2–3)

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[7CCE3ABF-C1A9-4184-A4AB-4FEEB035B76A](https://zoobank.org/7CCE3ABF-C1A9-4184-A4AB-4FEEB035B76A)

Type locality. Ukraine, Rivne Oblast (Rovno Province), mine unknown.

Type horizon. Upper Eocene, Priabonian stage (33.9–37.71 mya).

Holotype. Sex undetermined, in Rovno amber, deposited in the Fabrizio Fanti amber collection, accession No. RoA11UKR (donum Jonas Damzen: ex coll. JDC-12144R).

Differential diagnosis. *Mimoplatycis notha* Kazantsev, 2013, initially described from Baltic amber, has also been mentioned from Rovno amber (Kazantsev, 2013; Kazantsev & Perkovsky, 2014), but recently the latter specimen has been considered a different species, which will be described shortly

Fig. 3. *Mimoplatycis usa* sp. nov. in Rovno amber, reconstruction of the pronotum.

(Kazantsev et al., 2025). Subsequently, two more taxa were described from Baltic amber: *Mimoplatycis bicolor* Fanti & Vitali, 2017 and *M. marchettii* Parisi & Fanti, 2019 (Fanti & Vitali, 2017; Parisi & Fanti, 2019). The new species is easily recognisable from all the others due to its pronotal shape, with a conspicuous and subrectangular areole located attached to the posterior margin in the middle, while *M. marchettii* has a simple transversal carina, *M. notha* has a transversal carina with four additional vertical carinae, and *M. bicolor* has H-shaped carinae that are very wide (Kazantsev, 2013; Fanti & Vitali, 2017; Parisi & Fanti, 2019).

Description. Adult, winged, rather robust. Sex undetermined. Body length: about 3.1 mm. Entirely dark brown. Head short, strongly transverse, partially covered by pronotum, equipped with shallow punctuation and strongly pubescent. Eyes large, rounded, inserted in the upper-lateral part of the head. Mandibles not visible. Maxillary palps 4-segmented, fourth palpomere globular and distally pointed. Labial palps 3-segmented. Antennae filiform, 11-segmented, rather short, reaching the half-length of elytra; antennomere I slightly club-shaped, very elongated; antennomere II enlarged from middle to apex, about 1.7 times shorter than scape; antennomere III slightly longer and noticeably thinner than previous one; antennomeres IV-VIII elongated, sub-equal, longer than previous one; antennomeres IX-X subequal, slightly shorter than previous ones; antennomere XI elongated, filiform, rounded at apex; all antennomeres with sparse and long setae. Pronotum transverse, as wide as head at anterior margin, wider than head at

posterior margin, with impressed punctuation and slightly pubescent, prominent produced laterally posterior angles, anterior angles obtuse, surface with a conspicuous and subrectangular areole located attached to the posterior margin in the centre and delineated by evident carina, and a large and bulged central-transversal stripe rather wrinkled and interrupted in the middle, which has a very weak stripe / carina on each side that almost reaches the anterior margin. Scutellum very elongated, robust, rounded apically. Elytra elongated, parallel-sided, much wider than pronotum, substantially smooth and equipped with setae, apex not particularly rounded. Metathoracic wings infuscate, covered by elytra. Legs short, robust, pubescent; coxae robust; trochanters elongated, rounded apically; femora short, robust; tibiae cylindrical, thin, tibial spur small. Tarsal formula 5-5-5, tarsomeres rather stout; tarsomere I robust and elongated; tarsomere II about 1.6 times shorter than tarsomere I; tarsomere III almost triangular, short; tarsomere IV strongly bilobed, with lobes short and very robust and rounded apically; tarsomere V rather short, very robust, strongly curved; claws simple. Metasternum not visible. Abdomen presumably with six transverse ventrites.

Etymology. Derived from the United States of America (USA), the name honours this nation for its great contributions to technology, medicine, space exploration, zoology, palaeontology, and other sciences, as well as its emphasis on freedom and human rights. Specific epithet is to be treated as noun in apposition.

Syninclusions. A few detritus, botanical remains, and air bubbles.

Remarks. The green-yellowish amber piece, semicircular shaped, measures approximately 25×16×6 mm and weighs 1.6 grams. The inclusion's ventral parts are heavily covered with milky emulsion (German term: "Verlumung"). The amber piece has fractures and is quite opaque. The holotype appears complete.

World checklist of fossil soldier beetles

CRETACEOUS

Koonwarra Fossil Bed – Site NMVPL425 (Australia) [114.1–110 mya]:

1. *Chauliognathus (Chauliognathus) koonwarra* Fanti, 2022

Spanish amber (Spain) [110 mya]:

2. *Molliberus albae* Peris & Fanti, 2018

Burmese (Kachin) amber (Myanmar) [98.79 ± 0.62 mya]:

3. *Brevipterus acutiapicis* Y. Yang, H. Liu & W. Zhao in Zhao, Liu, Geiser & Yang, 2022
4. *Brevipterus megacephalus* Y. Yang, H. Liu & W. Zhao in Zhao, Liu, Geiser & Yang, 2022
5. *Brevipterus obtusiapicis* Y. Yang, H. Liu & W. Zhao in Zhao, Liu, Geiser & Yang, 2022
6. *Burmomiles blixenae* Fanti & Damgaard, 2019
7. *Burmomiles brevicollis* Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024b
8. *Burmomiles laticollis* Y. Yang, Geiser & H. Liu in Yang, Zhao, Geiser, Zhang, Bai & Liu, 2021
9. *Burmomiles parisii* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
10. *Burmomiles volpei* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
11. *Burmomiles willerslevorum* Fanti, Damgaard & Ellenberger, 2018
12. *Cretocantharis veda* Hsiao, Li, Ren & Pang, 2021
13. *Elektrokleinia bilineatimaculata* (Y. Yang, Geiser & H. Liu in Yang, Zhao, Geiser, Zhang, Bai & Liu, 2021)
14. *Elektrokleinia oblongoculus* (Y. Yang, Bai & W. Zhang in Yang, Zhao, Geiser, Zhang, Bai & Liu, 2021)
15. *Elektrokleinia panna* (Hsiao, Li, Ren & Pang, 2021)
16. *Elektrokleinia picta* Ellenberger & Fanti, 2019
17. *Elektrokleinia steffenseni* Fanti & Damgaard, 2020
18. *Elektrokleinia thiloi* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
19. *Elektrokleinia zahnradniki* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
20. *Hukawngichthyurus barsevskisi* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
21. *Hukawngichthyurus ditaddeoi* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
22. *Hukawngichthyurus kiawkhaingwini* Fanti & Ellenberger, 2018
23. *Hukawngichthyurus maha* Hsiao, Li, Ren & Pang, 2021
24. *Myamalycocerus vitalii* Fanti & Ellenberger, 2016
25. *Ornatomalthinus elvirae* Poinar & Fanti, 2016
26. *Poinarelektronmiles cuaroni* Bramanti & Fanti, 2022
27. *Poinarelektronmiles ellenbergeri* Fanti & Damgaard, 2020
28. *Sanaungulus angustipennis* (Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024b)
= *Burmomiles angustipennis* Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024a **unavailable name**
29. *Sanaungulus christensenae* Fanti & Damgaard, 2019
30. *Sanaungulus curtipennis* Fanti, Damgaard & Ellenberger, 2018
31. *Sanaungulus dentatus* (Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024b)
= *Burmomiles dentatus* Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024a **unavailable name**
32. *Sanaungulus dominikiweissbachi* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
33. *Sanaungulus dunlopi* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
34. *Sanaungulus electrum* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
35. *Sanaungulus elongaticollis* Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024a
36. *Sanaungulus emarginaticollis* Y. Yang, H. Liu & M. Bai in Yang, Zhao, Geiser, Zhang, Ren, Bai & Liu, 2022
37. *Sanaungulus fabriciusi* Fanti & Damgaard, 2019
38. *Sanaungulus franziskaeweissbachae* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
39. *Sanaungulus ghitaenoerbyae* Fanti, Damgaard & Ellenberger, 2018
40. *Sanaungulus havai* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
41. *Sanaungulus imparitibius* Y. Yang, H. Liu & W. Zhao in Yang, Zhao, Geiser, Zhang, Ren, Bai & Liu, 2022
42. *Sanaungulus kachinensis* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
43. *Sanaungulus kirstenaeweissbachae* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
44. *Sanaungulus laticoxa* Y. Yang, H. Liu & Ren in Yang, Zhao, Geiser, Zhang, Ren, Bai & Liu, 2022
45. *Sanaungulus leniae* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
46. *Sanaungulus lethi* Fanti & Damgaard, 2020
47. *Sanaungulus longicornis* Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024a
48. *Sanaungulus marginalis* Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024a
49. *Sanaungulus morellii* Fanti & Damgaard, 2020
50. *Sanaungulus multiramus* Y. Yang, H. Liu & W. Zhao in Yang, Zhao, Geiser, Zhang, Ren, Bai & Liu, 2022

51. *Sanaungulus myanmaricus* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
52. *Sanaungulus myitkyinaensis* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
53. *Sanaungulus nalae* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
54. *Sanaungulus nilsi* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
55. *Sanaungulus perkovskyi* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
56. *Sanaungulus peteriruedeli* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
57. *Sanaungulus recticollis* (Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024b)
58. *Sanaungulus rosenzweigi* Fanti & Damgaard, 2020
59. *Sanaungulus ruficollis* Y. Yang, H. Liu & W. Zhao in Yang, Zhao, Geiser, Zhang, Ren, Bai & Liu, 2022
60. *Sanaungulus ruicheni* (Hsiao & Huang, 2018)
61. *Sanaungulus strungei* Fanti & Damgaard, 2019
62. *Sanaungulus temporiscapsula* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
63. *Sanaungulus troelsikloevedali* Fanti & Damgaard, 2019
64. *Sanaungulus undecimus* Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024a **incertae sedis** (it is not a *Sanaungulus*)
65. *Sanaungulus ypogaeum* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
66. *Vitalfranzius burmiticus* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
67. *Vitalfranzius cretaceus* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022
68. *Archaeomalthodes rosetta* Hsiao, Ślipiński & Pang in Hsiao, Ślipiński, Deng & Pang, 2016
69. *Nothotythonyx serratus* Y.-D. Li, Biffi, Kundrata & Cai in Li, Biffi, Kundrata, Huang & Cai, 2022
- Agdzhakend amber (Azerbaijan) [ca. 98 mya]:
70. *Katyacantharis zherikhini* Kazantsev & Perkovsky, 2019
- PALEOCENE
- Quebrada “El Griton”, “Sunchal Formation” (Argentina) [65.5–56.0 mya]:
71. *Podabrus santaritensis* Cockerell, 1936
- EOCENE
- Baltic amber (Poland–Russia–Denmark) [47.8–41.2/37.8–33.9 mya]:
72. *Cacomorphocerus bentifabrici* Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
73. *Cacomorphocerus cerambyx* Schaufuss, 1892
74. *Cacomorphocerus coleae* Fanti & M. K. Pankowski, 2019
75. *Cacomorphocerus endecacerus* Poinar & Fanti, 2019
76. *Cacomorphocerus eocenicus* Bukejs, Fanti & McKellar, 2019
77. *Cacomorphocerus incurvus* Fanti & Vitali, 2023
78. *Cacomorphocerus jantarius* (Kuška & Kania, 2010)
79. *Cacomorphocerus madseni* Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
80. *Cacomorphocerus marki* Fanti & M. G. Pankowski, 2020
81. *Cacomorphocerus obstinatus* Parisi & Fanti, 2020
82. *Cacomorphocerus simkei* Fanti, 2024
83. *Cacomorphocerus thomasiwentzeli* Wentzel, Bonino & Fanti, 2022
84. *Cacomorphocerus wiszniewskii* Fanti & Kupryjanowicz, 2018
85. *Electronycha arturmichalskii* Fanti [present paper]
86. *Electronycha prussica* Kazantsev, 2013
87. *Eridanula susannaebierae* Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
88. *Michalskantharis bursztynica* Fanti, 2017
89. *Noergaardia dinae* Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
90. *Sucinocantharis baltica* Kuška & Kania, 2010
91. *Sucinorhagonycha carsteni* Fanti, 2023
92. *Sucinorhagonycha fabrizioi* M. G. Pankowski, 2023
93. *Sucinorhagonycha groehni* Kazantsev, 2020
94. *Sucinorhagonycha kulicka* Kuška, 1996
95. *Sucinorhagonycha maryae* M. G. Pankowski & Fanti, 2023
96. *Sucinorhagonycha samsokorum* Fanti & M. K. Pankowski, 2018
97. *Arturmiles pankowskii* Fanti, 2021
- A. *Cantharis* aff. *nigricans* Burmeister, 1832
98. *Cantharis* (*Cantharis*) *borki* Fanti & Damgaard, 2019

99. *Cantharis (Cantharis) crisantha* Fanti & M. G. Pankowski, 2020
100. *Cantharis (Cantharis) dougi* Kupryjanowicz & Fanti, 2019
101. *Cantharis (Cantharis) hanswernerii* Kazantsev, 2018
102. *Cantharis (Cantharis) hoffeinsorum* Kazantsev, 2018
103. *Cantharis (Cantharis) kviumi* Fanti & Damgaard, 2020
104. *Cantharis (Cantharis) raeorum* Fanti & M. G. Pankowski, 2020
105. *Cantharis (Cantharis) samsocki* M. G. Pankowski, 2023
106. *Cantharis (Cantharis) sucinonigra* Kuška, 1992
107. *Cantharis (Cyrtomoptila) mikkelsenorum* Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
108. *Cantharis (Cyrtomoptila) sucinokotejai* (Kuška, 1996)
109. *Juratelacrima ballingi* Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
110. *Lycocerus christelae* Kazantsev, 2018
111. *Lycocerus crassepunctatus* Kazantsev, 2021
112. *Lycocerus dentantennatus* Kazantsev, 2018
113. *Lycocerus elzbietae* Kazantsev, 2020
114. *Lycocerus jesperibuchi* Fanti & Damgaard, 2019
115. *Lycocerus jonasi* Kazantsev, 2020
116. *Lycocerus xenium* Fanti, 2020
117. *Palmnickeneoceras ejersboi* Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
118. *Podistra (Absidia) jirii* Fanti, 2020
119. *Podistra (Absidia) klovedali* Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
120. *Podistra (Absidia) mattheseni* Fanti & Damgaard, 2020
121. *Podistra (Podistra) guthriei* Fanti, 2021
122. *Podistra (Podistra) madelineae* M. G. Pankowski & Fanti, 2023
123. *Rhagonycha (Rhagonycha) acarigera* Kazantsev, 2020
124. *Rhagonycha (Rhagonycha) kryshstofovichi* (Yablokov-Khnzorian, 1960)
125. *Rhagonycha (Rhagonycha) maryae* Fanti & M. K. Pankowski, 2018
126. *Rhagonycha (Rhagonycha) nielsenae* Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
127. *Rhagonycha (Rhagonycha) sucinobaltica* Poinar & Fanti, 2016
128. *Themus (Haplothemus) bennyanderseni* Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
129. *Themus (Haplothemus) pristinus* Kazantsev, 2013
130. *Kuskaella bajerae* Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
131. *Kuskaella macroptera* Fanti & Kupryjanowicz, 2017
132. *Kuskaella petriolii* Fanti & Vitali, 2020
133. *Mantimalthinus arturi* Fanti, 2022
134. *Mantimalthinus balticus* Fanti & Castiglione, 2017
135. *Mantimalthinus bartholini* Fanti & Damgaard, 2019
136. *Malthinus (Malthinus) amicitiae* Fanti & Vitali, 2023
137. *Malthinus (Malthinus) danieli* Kuška & Kania, 2010
138. *Malthinus (Malthinus) fabriziofantii* M. V. Pankowski, 2024
139. *Malthinus (Malthinus) karenpankowskiae* M. G. Pankowski & Fanti, 2023
140. *Malthinus (Malthinus) masoni* M. G. Pankowski & Fanti, 2022
141. *Malthinus (Malthinus) pauljohnsoni* M. G. Pankowski & Fanti, 2023
142. *Malthinus (Malthinus) rifbjergi* Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
143. *Malthodes (Libertimalthodes) aphidiphagus* Fanti & Michalski, 2018
144. *Malthodes (Libertimalthodes) betseyae* M. G. Pankowski & Fanti, 2023
145. *Malthodes (Libertimalthodes) elytratus* Kupryjanowicz & Fanti, 2019
146. *Malthodes (Libertimalthodes) headsii* Fanti, 2021
147. *Malthodes (Libertimalthodes) jaredi* Fanti, 2021
148. *Malthodes (Libertimalthodes) spaceae* Fanti, 2019
149. *Malthodes (Malthodes) aliger* Kazantsev, 2021
150. *Malthodes (Malthodes) caenozoicus* Fanti & Vitali, 2017
151. *Malthodes (Malthodes) ceranowiczae* Kuška & Kupryjanowicz, 2005
152. *Malthodes (Malthodes) gedanicus* Fanti & Sontag, 2019
153. *Malthodes (Malthodes) giannii* Parisi & Fanti, 2020
154. *Malthodes (Malthodes) greenwalti* M. G. Pankowski & Fanti, 2023

155. *Malthodes (Malthodes) henningseni* Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
156. *Malthodes (Malthodes) immortalis* Parisi & Fanti, 2020
157. *Malthodes (Malthodes) josephi* Fanti & M. K. Pankowski, 2018
158. *Malthodes (Malthodes) kotejai* Kuška & Kupryjanowicz, 2005
159. *Malthodes (Malthodes) maierae* M. V. Pankowski & Fanti, 2024
160. *Malthodes (Malthodes) marialuisae* Parisi & Fanti, 2020
161. *Malthodes (Malthodes) markpankowskii* M. G. Pankowski & Fanti, 2022
162. *Malthodes (Malthodes) maximiliani* Fanti & M. V. Pankowski, 2024
163. *Malthodes (Malthodes) meriae* Fanti, 2018
164. *Malthodes (Malthodes) michalskii* Fanti, 2017
165. *Malthodes (Malthodes) moellehavei* Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
166. *Malthodes (Malthodes) nublar* Kupryjanowicz & Fanti, 2019
167. *Malthodes (Malthodes) serafini* Kuška & Kupryjanowicz, 2005
168. *Malthodes (Malthodes) sucini* Kuška & Kania, 2010
169. *Malthodes (Malthodes) sucinopenninus* Kuška & Kania, 2010
170. *Malthodes (Malthodes) tognettii* Parisi & Fanti, 2019
171. *Malthodes (Malthodes) unimol* Parisi & Fanti, 2020
172. *Malthodes (Malthodes) vallombrosa* Parisi & Fanti, 2024
173. *Mimoplatycis bicolor* Fanti & Vitali, 2017
174. *Mimoplatycis marchettii* Parisi & Fanti, 2019
175. *Mimoplatycis notha* Kazantsev, 2013
176. *Autosilis annisettaekoppela* Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
177. *Curche pauli* Alekseev & Kazantsev, 2014
178. *Electrosilis minuta* Kazantsev, 2013
179. *Markus karenae* Fanti & M. J. Pankowski, 2018
180. *Podosilis gedaniensis* Kazantsev, 2020
181. *Podosilis groehni* Bukejs & Fanti, 2023
182. *Silis (Silis) boninoi* Fanti & M. G. Pankowski, 2022
183. *Silis (Silis) carsteni* Bukejs & Fanti, 2023
184. *Silis (Silis) lombardii* Parisi & Fanti, 2019
- Bitterfeld amber (Germany) [47.8–38 mya]:
185. *Malthodes (Malthodes) andreasiabelei* Fanti, 2019 (replaced name of *M. andreasi* Fanti, 2019)
= *Malthodes (Malthodes) andreasi* Fanti, 2019
186. *Malthodes (Malthodes) neumanni* Fanti, 2019
- Rovno amber (Ukraine) [47.8–41.2/37.8–33.9 mya]:
187. *Cacomorphocerus meridionalis* Kazantsev & Perkovsky, 2020
188. *Cantharis (Cantharis) michaeli* Fanti & M. G. Pankowski, 2023
189. *Lycocerus albovacca* Kazantsev & Perkovsky in Kazantsev, Legalov & Perkovsky, 2024
190. *Malthodes (Malthodes) perkovskiyi* Kazantsev, 2010
191. *Malthodes (Malthodes) rovnoensis* Kazantsev & Perkovsky, 2014
192. *Mimoplatycis usa* Fanti [present paper]
- Sakhalinian amber (Sakhalin Island – Russia) [47.0–43.0 mya or 41.2–47.8 mya]:
193. *Cnathrion sakhalinense* Kazantsev & Perkovsky, 2019
- Insect Limestone, Gurnard Bay, NW Isle of Wight (England – United Kingdom) [38.0–33.9 mya]:
194. *Themus (?Telephorops) polyaki* Kirejtshuk in Kirejtshuk, Ponomarenko, Kurochkin, Alexeev, Gratshev, Solodovnikov, Krell & Soriano, 2019
- Florissant (USA) [34.07 ± 0.10 mya]:
195. *Atalantycha humata* (Wickham, 1913)
196. *Rhagonycha (Rhagonycha) hesperus* (Wickham, 1914)
197. *Podabrus cupesoides* Wickham, 1917
198. *Podabrus florissantensis* Wickham, 1914
199. *Podabrus fragmentatus* Wickham, 1914
200. *Podabrus wheeleri* Wickham, 1909
201. *Chauliognathus (Chauliognathus) pristinus* Scudder, 1876
202. *Trypherus aboriginalis* Wickham, 1913
203. *Polemium (Polemium) crassicornis* Wickham, 1914
- Aix-en-Provence (France) [? – Eocene/Oligocene]:
- B. cfr. *Autosilis nitidula* (Fabricius) – Serres, 1843 (extant species?)

OLIGOCENE

Brunstatt (France) [33.9–28.4 mya]:

204. *Malthodes (Malthodes) obtusus* B. Förster, 1891

Enspel (Germany) [24.9–24.5 mya]:

205. *Cantharis (Cantharis) doernerorum* Fanti & Poschmann, 2019
206. *Cantharis (Cantharis) zabolica* Fanti & Poschmann, 2019

Rott (Germany) [24.2–23.03 mya]:

207. *Cantharis (Cantharis) bradburyi* Fanti & Walker, 2019
208. *Cantharis (Cantharis) brodiei* (Heyden & Heyden, 1866)
209. *Cantharis (Cantharis) caduca* (Heyden & Heyden, 1866)
210. *Cantharis (Cantharis) carbonaria* (Heyden & Heyden, 1866)
211. *Cantharis (Cantharis) exauctarata* (Heyden & Heyden, 1866)
212. *Cantharis (Cantharis) lidiae* Fanti & Walker, 2019
213. *Cantharis (Cantharis) rottensis* Fanti & Walker, 2019
214. *Podistra (Absidia) quies* Fanti & Walker, 2019
215. *Rhagonycha (Rhagonycha) carolynae* Fanti & Walker, 2019
216. *Rhagonycha (Rhagonycha) ultramundana* Fanti & Walker, 2019

MIOCENE

Mexican (Chiapas) amber (Mexico) [13–19 mya, or 15–20 mya; also 13–22.8 mya]:

217. *Silis (Silis) chiapasensis* Wittmer, 1963

Radoboj (Croatia) [20–16 mya]:

218. *Cantharis (Cantharis) attavina* (Heer, 1847) see also *Rhagonycha (Rhagonycha) tertiaria* (Heer, 1847) from Öhningen

Dominican amber (Dominican Republic) [20–15 mya, probably close to 16 mya: 16–18]:

219. *Silis (Silis) curleri* Fanti & M. G. Pankowski, 2021

220. *Silis (Silis) hegnai* Fanti & M. G. Pankowski, 2021

221. *Tytthonyx (Tytthonyx) geiseri* Poinar & Fanti, 2016

222. *Tytthonyx (Tytthonyx) milleri* Ivie, Fanti & Ferreira, 2022

223. *Tytthonyx (Tytthonyx) stadili* Fanti & Damgaard, 2019

Shandong, Shanwang, Linqiu County (China) [16–11.6 mya]:

224. *Lycocerus guttula* (J. Zhang, 1989)

225. *Themus (Themus) capacis* (J. Zhang, 1989)

226. *Themus (Themus) thermophilus* (J. Zhang, 1989)

227. *Themus (Themus) trapezialis* (J. Zhang, Sun & X. Zhang, 1994)

Öhningen (Germany) [12.7–10 mya]:

228. *Cantharis (Cantharis) fragilis* (Heer, 1847)

229. *Cantharis (Cantharis) macilenta* (Heer, 1865)

230. *Rhagonycha (Rhagonycha) germari* (Heer, 1847)

231. *Rhagonycha (Rhagonycha) tertiaria* (Heer, 1847) (also from Radoboj, Croatia)

Vlădiceni (Romania) [around 10.5 mya]:

232. *Malthodes (Malthodes) vladiceniensis* Pintilioaie, Fanti & Ionesi, 2021

PLIOCENE

Lac Chambon (France) [3.6–2.6 mya]:

233. *Rhagonycha (Rhagonycha) micans* Piton, 1939

Checklist of extinct fossil genera of soldier beetles

The following list does not comprise genera which include extant species of the Cantharidae family.

Archaeomalthodes Hsiao, Ślipiński & Pang in Hsiao, Ślipiński, Deng & Pang, 2016

Arturmiles Fanti, 2021

Brevipterus Y. Yang, H. Liu & W. Zhao in Zhao, Liu, Geiser & Yang, 2022

Burmomiles Fanti, Damgaard & Ellenberger, 2018

Cacomorphocerus Schaufuss, 1892

= *Hoffeinsensia* Kuška & Kania, 2010

Cnathrion Kazantsev & Perkovsky, 2019
Cretocantharis Hsiao, Y. Li, Ren & Pang, 2021
Curche Alekseev & Kazantsev, 2014
Electronycha Kazantsev, 2013
Electrosilis Kazantsev, 2013
Elektrokleinia Ellenberger & Fanti, 2019
 = *Palaeocantharis* Hsiao, Y. Li, Ren & Pang, 2021
Eridanula Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
Hukawngichthyurus Fanti & Ellenberger, 2018
Juratelacrima Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
Katyacantharis Kazantsev & Perkovsky, 2019
Kuskaella Fanti & Kupryjanowicz, 2017
Mantimalthinus Fanti & Castiglione, 2017
Markus Fanti & M. J. Pankowski, 2018
Michalskantharis Fanti, 2017
Mimoplatycis Kazantsev, 2013
Molliberus Peris & Fanti, 2018
Myamalycocerus Fanti & Ellenberger, 2016
Noergaardia Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
Nothotythyonyx Y.-D. Li, Biffi, Kundrata & Cai in Li, Biffi, Kundrata, Huang & Cai, 2022
Ornatomalthinus Poinar & Fanti, 2016
Palmnickeneoceras Fanti & Damgaard, 2018
Poinarelektronmiles Fanti & Damgaard, 2020
Sanaungulus Fanti, Damgaard & Ellenberger, 2018
Sucinocantharis Kuška & Kania, 2010
Sucinorhagonycha Kuška, 1996
Vitalfranzius Fanti & P. Müller, 2022

Tribes and subgenus:

Malthodes (*Libertimalthodes*) Kupryjanowicz & Fanti, 2019 (subgenus)
 Cacomorphocerini Fanti & Kupryjanowicz, 2018 (tribe)
 Mimoplatycini Kazantsev, 2013 (tribe)
 Nothotythyonychini Fanti, 2022 (tribe)

Taxonomical notes and information

†*Lithocantharis lunglokshuiensis* Lin in Lin & Lee, 1997 and †*Wongyekokia angustris* Lin in Lin & Lee, 1997 were recently transferred from the family Cantharidae to the family Carabidae (Fanti, 2022).

†*Sanaungulus kirstenaeweissbachae* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022 as cited in the original description has a very large and rounded last sternite (Fanti & Müller, 2022), a character indicating a female soldier beetle

(e.g., *Cantharis*, *Rhagonycha*, etc.), thus contradicting the attribution of a male specimen by Yang et al. (2024a), based on the antennal shape. While, †*Poinarelektronmiles cuaroni* Bramanti & Fanti, 2022 is listed as “sex undefined” in the original description (Bramanti & Fanti, 2022); the attribution to male by Yang et al. (2024a) is somewhat uncertain and unlikely for the same reason given above.

†*Podistra* (*Podistra*) *guthriei* Fanti, 2021 was originally placed in the subgenus *Pseudoabsidia* Wittmer, 1969 (Fanti, 2021). This subgenus was recently synonymised with *Podistra* Motschulsky, 1839 (Kazantsev, 2023b), but the subgeneric taxonomy is still uncertain and remains highly controversial (e.g., Krauss, 1894; Ganglbauer, 1922; 1931; Wittmer, 1969, 1973; Yang & Yang, 2012; Kazantsev, 2023a, 2023b).

Yang et al. (2024a) placed *Sanaungulus* with filiform antennae (the other species have pectinate antennae) as incertae sedis or as subfamily (Cantharidae) incertae sedis. This is an incorrect use of taxonomy. In fact, in the same paper, the authors (Yang et al., 2024a), simply consider the filiform antennae as a sexually dimorphic character, present in females but not in males. The *Sanaungulus* with filiform antennae therefore undoubtedly have exactly the same taxonomic position as the others. Not even to consider them as *Sanaungulus* as in Yang et al. (2024a) seems to be a mistake.

Yang et al. (2021, 2022) had already corrected (hypothetically), the position of the antennomeres of some species of *Sanaungulus* and *Burmomiles*. Subsequently, as can be seen from the text, two authors, Bramanti & Fanti (2022), during the original description of *Poinarelektronmiles cuaroni*, paid considerable attention to the positioning of the antennomeres of this species. In the subsequent paper by Yang et al. (2024a), the positioning of the antennomeres of *P. cuaroni*, *P. ellenbergeri*, *S. lethi*, *S. kirstenaeweissbachae* and *S. perkovskyi* was newly, but erroneously, corrected. The position of the antennae of *P. cuaroni* should therefore be considered, without any doubt, the original one (Bramanti & Fanti, 2022). Furthermore, as already stated in Bramanti & Fanti (2022), the documentation that the position of the antenna differs by half a millimetre from the original description is a taxonomically insignificant detail.

Among other things, Yang et al. (2024a) referred to *S. kirstenaeweissbachae* as *Burmomiles kirstenaeweissbachae* on page 170, but as *Sanaungulus kirstenaeweissbachae* in the rest of the text. In addition, Yang et al. (2024a), reported in their supplementary material, but also to a lesser extent in the text, the lengths of the antennomeres and their appendages, the elytral length and the body length of some Burmese amber specimens. These data are based on paper and computer screen illustrations and may not be entirely accurate.

†*Trapezioceps* Qu, Jarzembowski & Luo in Qu, Jarzembowski, Xiao & Luo, 2023

†*Trapezioceps longelytrum* Qu, Jarzembowski & Luo in Qu, Jarzembowski, Xiao & Luo, 2023

= †*Trapezioceps longelytrus* Kunderata, Packova, Li, Hsiao, Shaw, Ferreira, Bai & Cai, 2023: 3

unjustified emendation*

Ross, 2024a: 154, 2024b: 35 (*Mysteriomorphus longelytrus*).

In agreement with Kunderata et al. (2023), the genus †*Trapezioceps* is not a representative of the family Cantharidae as proposed by Qu et al. (2023), but is a member of the fossil family †*Mysteriomorphidae* Alekseev & Ellenberger, 2019 (Kunderata et al., 2023; Ross, 2024a, 2024b).

**longelytrum* = “long elytron”. Kunderata et al. (2023) consider *Trapezioceps* masculine in gender and “*longelytrum*” to be an adjective. Since *longelytrum* is evidently a noun in apposition, the emendation *longelytrus* is unjustified and not in prevailing usage (ICZN, 1999: Art. 33.2.).

Therefore, *Mysteriomorphus longelytrum* (Qu, Jarzembowski & Luo, 2023) is the correct name.

†*Poinarelektronmiles* Fanti & Damgaard, 2020

bonum genus

†*Poinarelektronmiles ellenbergeri* Fanti &

Damgaard, 2020 **comb. rest.**

†*Poinarelektronmiles cuaroni* Bramanti & Fanti,

2022 **comb. rest.**

Poinarelektronmiles Fanti & Damgaard, 2020 is well differentiated from *Burmomiles* Fanti, Damgaard & Ellenberger, 2018 for having, in addition to other characteristics, long elytra covering the last abdominal segments and a decidedly slimmer habitus. In fact, in the original description, if anything, the proximity to the genus *Myamalycocerus* Fanti & Ellenberger, 2016 (Fanti &

Damgaard, 2020) and not to *Burmomiles* is correctly highlighted. Recently, Yang et al. (2024a) have, erroneously, proposed the synonymy of *Poinarelektronmiles* with *Burmomiles*, and even moved the two species originally into *Poinarelektronmiles*: *P. ellenbergeri* Fanti & Damgaard, 2020 and *P. cuaroni* Bramanti & Fanti, 2022 to two different genera, respectively *Burmomiles* Fanti, Damgaard & Ellenberger, 2018 and *Sanaungulus* Fanti, Damgaard & Ellenberger, 2018. These genera, however, have enormously different characteristics from each other, as well as very different characters from *Poinarelektronmiles* (for example *Poinarelektronmiles* has a rounded head, while *Sanaungulus* has a triangular head). For Yang et al. (2024a) elytral length is not a character with taxonomic value; however, in a work by the same authors (Zhao et al., 2022: keys), elytral length becomes a valid diagnostic character. The elytral length is often an evolutionary and “structural” character; however, it can certainly change based on extreme environmental conditions such as high mountains, which cannot have happened during the formation of Burmese amber due to the lack, as well as Baltic amber (Sadowski, 2017), of a consistent orography. In fact, in living taxa we find a wide range of genera with long elytra or with shortened or very shortened elytra (e.g., *Macrocerus*, *Malthinus* and *Malthodes*), which no taxonomist would dream of synonymising. Furthermore, the entire taxonomy of the Cantharidae at a generic level, as is well known, is based heavily on characters with a taxonomic value similar to the elytral length, such as for example the shape of the claws or even the tooth at their base. In other genera we even find the diagnostic character between two or more genera to be only the shape of the tibiae (Švihla, 2004) with identical morphology and aedeagus (e.g., *Tibiopodabrus* respect *Micro-podabrus* and *Pseudopodabrus*) or, taking a genus described own by Yang et al. (2022), two genera have absolutely identical morphology (including elytra) with only small aedeagic differences (e.g., *Amphimorphus* respect *Cephalomalthinus*). Therefore, *Poinarelektronmiles* is a very different genus from *Burmomiles*, and the taxa *Poinarelektronmiles ellenbergeri* and *P. cuaroni* remain in the original genus and not respectively in *Burmomiles* and *Sanaungulus* as erroneously proposed by Yang et al. (2024a). Furthermore, *P. cuaroni* also has a rounded head, while the main diagnostic character of *Sanaungulus*

is having a strongly triangular head, as well as very shortened and deescent elytra (Fanti & Damgaard, 2020; Bramanti & Fanti, 2022; Fanti & Müller, 2022).

As we see, Yang et al. (2021, 2022, 2024a) place antennal diversity, i.e., the shape and arrangement of antennomeres or pectinate antennae compared to filiform antennae, as a generic level diagnostic character. In doing so, they move and therefore they absolutely fail to place (Yang et al., 2024a: page 177 (Appendix) many species in their correct genera. That's surprising because these species have very stable and above all well differentiated characters, and thus a very clear and irrefutable taxonomy.

†*Sanaungulus lethi* Fanti & Damgaard, 2020 **comb. rest.**

†*Sanaungulus dominikiweissbachi* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022 **comb. rest.**

†*Sanaungulus kachinensis* Fanti & P. Müller, 2022 **comb. rest.**

Sanaungulus lethi, *S. dominikiweissbachi*, and *S. kachinensis* are undoubtedly *Sanaungulus* Fanti, Damgaard & Ellenberger, 2018 because they have strongly shortened elytra (tendentially dehiscent) and a strongly triangular head. These characteristics, among other things, can be easily observed and are clearly described in Fanti & Damgaard (2020); in addition, the *Sanaungulus* species mentioned above are very different compared to *Burmomiles* Fanti, Damgaard & Ellenberger, 2018. The features cited in Yang et al. (2024a) are significant differences of a specific level and not of a generic level. Therefore, the attribution of the three species to the genus *Burmomiles* proposed by Yang et al. (2024a) has to be rejected in toto.

†*Sanaungulus ruficollis* Y. Yang, H. Liu & W. Zhao in Yang et al., 2022 **inappropriate name**

The authors say that the species has a red neck (pronotum), but as Fanti & Müller (2022) have already noted, the pronotum and head are clearly brown, as evidenced by the original photo, and the red colour is not real but due to the position of the inclusion and the incidence of the light used to take the photographs. Therefore on the basis of the Code (ICZN, 1999: Glossary), *Sanaungulus ruficollis* is an inappropriate name because the name denotes a character not possessed by the taxon bearing the name.

†*Sanaungulus undecimus* Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024a **incertae sedis**

This species certainly cannot belong to the genus *Sanaungulus* due to its round head, whereas in *Sanaungulus* the head is strongly narrowed behind the eyes. Unfortunately, *S. undecimus* has been described without having a preserved abdomen (Yang et al., 2024a: page 167) and its real taxonomic position cannot therefore be defined with certainty. It appears to be related to the genus *Poinarelektronmiles*. Therefore, *S. undecimus* is incertae sedis.

†*Sanaungulus angustipennis* (Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024b) **comb. nov.**
= *Burmomiles angustipennis* Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024a: 156 (Table 1), 168 (Table 2), Supplementary material (page 4) **unavailable name**

Burmomiles angustipennis is an unavailable name (ICZN, 1999: Glossary) because it does not conform to Art. 16.4. of the Code (ICZN, 1999). There is no fixation of the holotype, and there is no indication whether it is deposited in a collection and in which one.

Sanaungulus angustipennis (Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024b) having strongly shortened and dehiscent elytra and a strongly triangular head, is here transferred from the genus *Burmomiles* (original description) to *Sanaungulus*.

†*Sanaungulus dentatus* (Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024b) **comb. nov.**
= *Burmomiles dentatus* Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024a: 156 (Table 1), 168 (Table 2), Supplementary material (page 4) **unavailable name**

Burmomiles dentatus is an unavailable name (ICZN, 1999: Glossary) because it does not conform to Art. 16.4. of the Code (ICZN, 1999). There is no fixation of the holotype, and there is no indication whether it is deposited in a collection and in which one.

Sanaungulus dentatus (Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024b) having strongly shortened and dehiscent elytra and a strongly triangular head, is here transferred from the genus *Burmomiles* (original description) to *Sanaungulus*.

†*Sanaungulus recticollis* (Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024b) **comb. nov.**

Sanaungulus recticollis (Y. Yang, W. Zhao & H. Liu, 2024b) having strongly shortened and dehiscent ely-

tra and a triangular head behind eyes, is here transferred from the genus *Burmomiles* (original description) to *Sanaungulus*. Furthermore, *Sanaungulus rec-ticollis* is not complete as indicated in the original description (Yang et al., 2024b), because the left antenna is only preserved up to the ninth antennomere.

†*Sanaungulus strungei* Fanti & Damgaard, 2019

comb. rest.

This taxon has a head rather rounded in dorsal view, and triangular in ventral view (Fanti & Damgaard, 2019), but does not have an elongated neck, therefore the move to *Brevipterus* made by Zhao et al. (2022) is here considered erroneous. The species, is thus considered here a *Sanaungulus* as in the original description (Fanti & Damgaard, 2019).

The key present in Yang et al. (2024b) is largely unusable and not very useful because species of two completely different genera are mixed.

As noted by Kazantsev (2023c), *Podistra* representatives are distributed and diverse mainly on the northern slopes of the Greater Caucasus, many of them at high altitude. Kazantsev (2023c) however, also states that because the Greater Caucasus was separated from the sea or straits until the Mid-Late Miocene, the Alpine-type settlement with subsequent isolation and diversification occurred here after the Pleistocene glaciations, and thus *Podistra* is historically young and postglacial. That, according to the author, supports, the presence in the Eocene of *Lycocerus* instead of *Podistra* (Kazantsev, 2020, 2023c). Yet the areas where Eocene Baltic amber was formed was divided by the sea, the Turgay Strait, and the climate was very warm then. Thus, the presence of the genera *Themus*, *Lycocerus* and *Podosilis* in this resin and other Eocenian deposits (Kazantsev, 2013, 2018, 2020, 2021; Fanti & Damgaard, 2018, 2019; Kirejtshuk et al., 2019; Fanti, 2020; Bukejs & Fanti, 2023), would be peculiar based on Kazantsev's writing. In fact, given that these genera also adapted to high altitudes, why should they have become extinct in Europe with the Oligocene cooling and instead diversified in Asia? It's important to note that currently, *Podistra* is present in the Alps and reaches as far as the northern Apennines in Tuscany, Italy (Fanti, 2014), but does not reach Abruzzo and Southern Italy. Like many other insects, *Podistra* must have remained isolated on these latter Italian mountains as a glacial relict, and

should have diversified a lot. Therefore, the genus *Podistra* does not appear to be young at all, nor postglacial in origin. Its presence in Eocene amber is thus certain (Fanti, 2020, 2021) as for the genus *Lycocerus* and the others mentioned above, but perhaps for different ecological reasons. Based on the data of Kazantsev (2023c) we can perhaps say that *Podistra* is postglacial in a particular and restricted part of its distribution, but the origin of the genus itself is certainly not postglacial. More study is needed on this genus to determine its origin.

Discussion

The list of fossil species belonging to Cantharidae Imhoff, 1856 updated to 31 December 2024 comprises as many as 233 species (including the two species described in this paper) grouped in 47 genera. Of these, 31 genera are extinct and therefore known only as fossils. The taxa cover a time frame ranging from the Cretaceous (about 115–118 mya) to the Pliocene (Pleistocene-Holocene including subfossils). The new checklist of world fossil soldier beetles underscores the enormous increase in data and knowledge that occurred in the last seven years after the previous world catalog of Fanti (2017). It is also highlights the amount of research still needed on this family to better understand the biogeography, taxonomy, evolution, ecology and phylogeny of these intriguing insects (Brancucci, 1980; Kazantsev, 2013; Fanti, 2017, 2022; Motyka et al., 2023). Taxonomy is a very important discipline in entomology, and one that should be used with extreme care (Stoch, 2005). In recent years, however, too many papers have been based on less-than-rigorous research, damaging their scientific value (Stoch, 2005). That's unfortunate because rigorous studies of soldier beetles are more important now than ever.

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